

Phase Space Uncertainty in Quantum Mechanics and the Bose-Einstein Distribution

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. June 5, 2020

In previous notes, we argued that the Bose-Einstein distribution may be obtained through reaction balance, noting that the probability for a boson to scatter into a state containing $f(e_i)$ bosons is enhanced by $f(e_i)+1$. Thus, for $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$, $f(e_1)[1+f(e_3)] f(e_2) [1+f(e_4)] = f(e_3) [1+f(e_1)] f(e_4) [1+f(e_2)]$. Taking \ln of the latter and linking to the former yields the BE distribution. As shown in (1), the enhancement factor $f(e_i)+1$ is due to lack of resolution of (final scattered) particle states (particularly momentum direction) in phase space. This lack of resolution in quantum mechanics seems to be linked to the uncertainty principle. Thus, without any factorial arrangement scheme, but using reaction balance one may obtain the BE distribution. As argued, however, the enhancement factor is due to lack of resolution in phase space, thus it seems one may maximize uncertainty (in phase space) in the case of a certain amount of degeneracy (and subject to energy and average particle number constraints). For a very high degeneracy compared to the number of particles in an element of phase space one essentially has the classical or Maxwell-Boltzmann case, as shown in a previous note (3). When quantum uncertainty becomes important, there is lower degeneracy (due to the uncertainty principle) and the BE distribution appears. Thus, we argue in this note, that boson reaction balance (with the boson scattering enhancement) and the phase space with low degeneracy (i.e. a lack of resolution of some states) factorial approach are based on essentially the same physics. (It is already known they yield the same BE distribution.)

Boson Enhancement Factor of $f(e_i)+1$

If a boson scatters into a state e_i containing $f(e_i)$ bosons, there is an enhancement of $f(e_i)+1$. This follows from the result of (1): $P(n \text{ bosons in } e_i) = n! P(n \text{ distinguishable particles in } e_i)$. Thus, indistinguishability is emphasized as the main factor in the boson result, but there is a second idea, namely that final scattering states are almost identical i.e. there is a lack of resolution in phase space. This is also key to obtaining the result of (1).

In (1), it is explained that one may have a set of n bosons $a, b, c \dots$ scattering into final states $1, 2, 3, \dots$. The bosons are indistinguishable, thus $a \rightarrow 1 \ b \rightarrow 2$ etc is the same as $b \rightarrow 1 \ a \rightarrow 2$. Thus, there are $n!$ ways of linking the a, b, c 's with the $1, 2, 3$'s. In quantum mechanics, one adds amplitudes and then squares. Thus: one has $| a_1 b_2 \dots + a_2 b_1 \dots + \text{etc} |^2$. A key idea (1) is that one may not distinguish between the final states $1, 2, 3, 4$ etc. If these all had the same magnitude of energy, one might argue that the momenta angles were slightly different, but one was unable to distinguish. Thus, $a_1 = a_2 = a_3$ etc and one has $| n! a^* b^* c^* \dots |^2$. It is then further argued that an integral over detector area $dS_1 \ dS_2 \dots \ dS_n = n! (\Delta S)^n$. Thus, one is over counting the area and needs to divide by $n!$. The final result is $(n!^* n!)/n!$ Or $n!$. From this the boson enhancement factor in reactions emerges. Thus, the two key results, we argue, are indistinguishability and lack of resolution of phase space.

Factorial Degeneracy Arguments of Statistical Mechanics

Statistical mechanics texts (2) often use a factorial degeneracy argument to derive the BE distribution. They argue that one may consider a state e_i with a degeneracy of $g(e_i)=g_i$. For example, $g(e_i)$ may be $d^3p dV / h^3$. The Planck constant is associated with the uncertainty principle. If there is no uncertainty, i.e. g_i is very large, one essentially has the classical MB case as shown in a previous note (3). If there is uncertainty, one cannot distinguish each point in a phase space unit i.e. two momenta with slightly different angles appear the same. This is exactly the same argument used in (1) except there all final scattering states 1,2,3,4 are the same. With the degeneracy argument, one does not force all states within $d^3p dV$ to be the same, but one lowers their resolution using g_i . It is the lowering of resolution which seems to yield the BE distribution.

Thus, one wishes to maximize uncertainty in the direction of momentum p (or position) (or the phase space unit in general which also contains the position vectors) subject to a looser number of degenerate cells, each with the same energy e_i . For the classical nonrelativistic case and a given e_i , every momentum point on the surface of a sphere is distinguishable, so one maximizes uncertainty with respect to this (i.e. $g_i \gg n_i$) and obtains an MB distribution from:

$$\ln(\text{Number of arrangements}) = \sum \text{over } i \ln\{ [n_i + g_i - 1]! / [n_i! (g_i - 1)!] \} \quad ((1))$$

This is based on using partitions and particles and forming all arrangements. If one maximizes ((1)) subject to: $\sum \text{over } i n_i = N$ and $\sum \text{over } i e_i n_i = E$, one obtains the BE distribution. If $g_i \gg n_i$, one obtains the MB distribution, which follows as a limit of the BE distribution.

Thus, the physics behind maximizing uncertainty of arrangements based on a certain degeneracy within phase space (which is reduced due to the quantum mechanical uncertainty principle it seems) appears to be the same as the statement that the probability of a boson to scatter into a state with $f(e_i)$ bosons is enhanced by $f(e_i)+1$.

Grand Canonical Considerations

It is known from the literature (2) that one may obtain the Bose-Einstein distribution using a grand canonical partition function which does not hold the total number of particles fixed. How is this related to the above arguments? For the factorial arrangement scheme, one imagines different arrangements of n_i particles in the degenerate units associated with e_i . Thus, for the two to be the same, n_i must represent an average number of particles which may be present within the degenerate units of the phase space cell. How may one see this?

First, it should be noted that for the Maxwell-Boltzmann case there is no average of total N , yet the Bose-Einstein and MB results both emerge from the same factorial expression ((1)) and have the same constraints. Thus, one has to be careful in interpreting constraints. In the MB case, $g \gg n_i$ and the two constraint Lagrange multipliers become separable after performing a variation of n_i . Thus, one may obtain a probability, in the MB case, independent of N , namely $P(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/T) / [\sum \text{over } i \exp(-e_i/T)]$. This allows one to create an overall probability with a

fixed N or a partition function for independent particles $(\exp(-e_1/T) + \exp(-e_2/T) + \dots)^N$. This immediately shows that N is fixed, but total energy may vary. In other words, a canonical approach is used. For the Bose-Einstein case, the two Lagrange multipliers do not separate i.e. $f(e_i) = 1 / [\exp((e_i - u)/T)]$. Thus, $f(e_i)$ cannot be converted into a probability independent of N , so one cannot write $(f(e_1) + f(e_2) + \dots)^N$ for a fixed N . This seems to imply that one does not have a fixed N , suggesting there is an average of macrostate N 's yielding an average $\langle N \rangle$. By simply examining the constraint $\sum_i n_i = N$ (used for both the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Bose-Einstein case), this is not immediately apparent.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the idea of loss of resolution (say of the direction of momenta vectors) in a phase space cell $d^3p dV$, allows one to try to maximize uncertainty within this set of degenerate units all with the same e_i subject to energy and particle number constraint. If the degeneracy increases to include all momentum and positions with the phase space cell, one has the classical Maxwell-Boltzmann case, otherwise, one obtains the Bose-Einstein result for bosons. The lack of resolution of phase space is also a key argument in the derivation of the result: $P(n \text{ bosons in } e_i) = n! P(n \text{ different particles in } e_i)$. In the derivation of this result, it is assumed that one may not resolve slightly different final momentum vectors. Thus, there is a loss of resolution of phase space. This yields an enhancement factor of $f(e_i)+1$ for a boson to scatter into a state e_i which has $f(e_i)$ bosons.

In the factorial maximization case, the loss of resolution does not allow the Lagrange multiplier for particle number to decouple from that related to energy when varying $n(e_i)$. Thus, the distribution (BE) depends on $(e_i - u)/T$ and one does not have an N independent probability for a single particle. As a result, one may not write $(f(e_1) + f(e_2) + \dots)^N$ suggesting there is not a fixed N , but rather an average over macrostates with different numbers of total particles, but with an overall average of $\langle N \rangle = N$.

References

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